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Mineral sequestration of CO₂ from Vernasca Ca-looping demo system: scale up to a pilot

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Abstract

In recent years, carbon sequestration into thermodynamically stable carbonates has been developed as a promising carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS) method, especially, when alkaline industrial wastes are used as sorbents. The use of industrial wastes to sequester CO₂ plays a dual role in environment protection, creating opportunities not only for capture and disposal of CO₂ but also for recycling of wastes and promoting the transition to circular economy. The CLEANKER project (Horizon 2020 Project Clean clinker production by Calcium looping process) aims to build a CO₂ mineralization pilot incorporated into Ca-looping demo system in Vernasca cement plant and use the re-carbonated wastes in concrete applications.

Different types of wastes such as burnt oil shale (BOS) from Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants as well as from Enefit280 oil producing unit in Estonia, concrete demolition wastes (CDW), cement by-pass dust (CBD) from Robilante, Italy, blast furnace slag (NSF) from Bremen, Germany were tested first in laboratory scale via dry and wet direct carbonation routes under the conditions of CO₂-rich model gas flow of 70 – 100% CO₂, simulating the Ca-looping system. The results show that selected types of BOS and cement wastes could be used as efficient binders in both dry and wet CO₂ mineralization systems with binding capacities up to 0.18 kg of CO₂ per kg of BOS and up to 0.24 kg of CO₂ per kg of CBD. The activating effect of hydration as a pre-treatment method showed that at lower operating temperatures, the same level of CO₂ capture can be achieved, thereby rendering the carbonization processes of similar industrial wastes more energy efficient. Moreover, the CO₂ mineralization tests with BOS in a 46 L concrete mixer confirmed the applicability of wet carbonization process also in larger scale.

Based on the results, the most promising materials, BOS and CBD, were selected for in the proposed CO₂-mineralization process in wet conditions at ambient temperature. The pilot (200 L) was designed based on a commercially available concrete mixer integrated into CLEANKER Ca-looping demo system and equipped with CO₂ inlets and outlets, as well as CO₂, temperature and moisture sensors to detect the reaction progress. The re-carbonated wastes will be tested via concrete casting in order to demonstrate the quality of the commercial product in the following stages of the project.

Keywords: CCUS; Ca-looping; CO₂ mineralization

1. Introduction

CO₂ mineralization into thermodynamically stable carbonates is one of the CCUS methods. Using industrial wastes, such as power plant ashes, cement kiln and bypass dust, concrete demolition wastes, iron and steelmaking slags, municipal solid waste incinerator ashes and mine tailings, as CO₂ binders has a number of advantages, because these

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materials are generated usually in the vicinity of CO₂ point source emissions, supply a readily available source of CaO and/or Ca-silicates without the need for mining and grinding, and utilizing the carbonation product in construction materials could make the process profitable [1, 2]. Current study focuses on the solid wastes from power industry – such as burnt oil shale, and construction industry – such as concrete demolition wastes and cement by-pass dust. Estonia is still mostly utilizing low calorific fuel – oil shale as a primary source. This heavy fossil fuel dependence produces abundant amounts of ash consisting up to 25% of free lime [3-5]. Cement bypass dusts and concrete demolition wastes are characterized by high contents of free lime [6] and cement hydrate [7, 8], respectively. By using accelerated carbonation, it is possible to improve the quality of recycled concrete aggregate and waste cement as well as balance the CO₂ cycle. Since producing ton of cement emits around 0.87 ton of CO₂, the cement industry is globally accountable for up to 7% of annual anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [9]. According to the studies of International Energy Agency and EU Zero Emissions Platform cement industry should contribute to the largest CO₂ emissions drop through CCUS in Europe, in order to meet the target of 2 °C of global temperature increase [10, 11].

The main objective of the study was the design of a large (> 100 L) CO₂ mineralization reactor integrated with the CLEANKER pilot plant in Vernasca based on the outcome of lab-scale experiments on burnt oil shale ashes, cement by-pass dust and concrete demolition wastes carbonation. The reactor will allow to mineralize part of the CO₂ captured by Ca-looping during CLEANKER experimental campaigns.

Nomenclature

CCUS	carbon capture, utilization and storage
BOS	burnt oil shale
CBD	cement by-pass dust
CFB	circulating fluidized bed
CDW	concrete demolition wastes
ESPA	electrostatic precipitator ash
PP	power plant
PF	pulverized firing
NSF	blast furnace slag
TC	total carbon
BET	Brunauer–Emmett–Teller method
SSA	specific surface area
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
TGA	thermogravimetric analyzer
CM	concrete mixer
fCaO	free lime
XRF	X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy
XRD	X-ray diffraction

2. Laboratory-scale studies

2.1. Collecting representative samples

Solid wastes from different sectors were utilized in CO₂ mineralization process. The BOS1, BOS3 and BOS7 represent burnt oil shale samples from electrostatic precipitators (ESPA) and BOS2, BOS4 and BOS8 represent burnt oil shale samples from total ash silo of circulating fluidized bed (CFB) boilers of Eesti, Balti and Auvere power plants (PP), respectively (<https://www.energia.ee/en/tehnoloogia/elektri-ja-sooja-tootmine>) in February 2018. The pulverized firing (PF) ash sample BOS5 was collected from an SO₂ removal system (Novel Integrated Desulphurization, Alstom Power) in February 2018. The BOS6 sample was collected from Enefit 280 units that produce shale oil (<https://www.energia.ee/en/tehnoloogia/oli-tootmine>) in January – February 2018.

Two different suppliers of concrete demolition wastes made their material available for testing: I.L.C. s.r.l (Rondissone, TO, <https://www.ilcsabbiaeghiaia.com/>) and Isoltrasporti (Isola Sant'Antonio, AL, www.isoltrasporti.it). Fine fraction of recycled demolition waste (CDW1 and CDW3), fine fraction from demolition waste selectively derived from concrete (CDW2) and fine fraction of recycled demolition waste submitted to washing process (CDW4) were tested.

Additionally, a sample of cement by-pass dust (BPD) from Robilante (Italy) and a sample of blast furnace (NSF) slag from Bremen (Germany) were added to the experimental matrix (Table). The period of sampling was in September 2018 for BPD and June 2017 for NSF slag sample.

2.2. Analysis methods

The materials were analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy (Rigaku Primus II) and quantitative X-ray diffraction (XRD, Bruker D8 Advanced) at Department of Geology, University of Tartu.

The contents of free lime (fCaO), by ethylene glycol method and total carbon (TC) using Electra CS - 580 Carbon/Sulfur Determinator were determined. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) specific surface area (SSA) and the particle size distribution were determined using a Kelvin 1042 sorptometer and Horiba laser scattering particle size distribution analyzer LA-950, respectively.

The initial and carbonated samples were analyzed also with FTIR spectrometer ALPHA in order to compare mineralogical changes. FTIR measurements were recorded in the 400 – 4000 cm^{-1} region.

2.3. Experimental procedure

The dry carbonation route was studied at isothermal heating (400°C and 500°C) with BOS and CBD samples using a Setaram Setsys Evo 1750 thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA). During the experiments, standard 100 μL Al_2O_3 crucibles were used and 10 ± 0.5 mg of the sample was weighted. Thereafter a Nabertherm rotating tube furnace (Fig. 1) with maximum temperature of 1200 °C and furnace tube diameter of 70 – 90 mm was utilized to test applicability of the process on a larger scale. The effect of hydration and milling of the samples on CO_2 uptake and rate was also evaluated. In addition, kinetic calculations were performed based on experimental measurements. Various reaction models were compared to explain the mechanism of the carbonization process. Changes in sample mineralogical composition and physical properties were monitored by chemical analysis, FTIR and BET methods.

Fig. 1. Nabertherm rotating tube furnace

The wet carbonation route [2, 12, 13] – using liquid to solid ratio of 0.2 – 0.3 w/w was conducted in a semi-batch Eirich EL1 type intensive mixer. The wastes were treated under different operating regimes by varying rotation speed from 300 to 3000 rpm, CO_2 concentration in model gas from 20 to 70% (imitating the gas composition from Ca-looping pilot), gas flow from 30 to 400 L/h and the mass of initial sample from 150 to 600 g, (see Table). The mixing

pan was operated at slower speed (85 rpm) throughout the experiments. For process scale-up the experiments were carried out also in a 46 L concrete mixer (CM) equipped with gas inlets and outlets. The experiments were conducted in similar conditions as compared to Eirich EL1 type-mixer, but the material load and gas flows were increased up to 10 times (see Table).

Table. List of samples and wet carbonation route operation regimes.

Sample	Explanation	CO ₂ % in gas	V (gas), L/h	M (solid), g	Rotation speed, rpm	Reactor type
BOS1	Eesti PP ESPA1	20	100	150	300-3000	EL1
BOS2	Eesti PP total ash	20-70	200	150	300-3000	EL1
BOS3	Balti PP ESPA1	20-70	30-400	150-600	300-3000	EL1
		70	400-2000	1000-6000		CM
BOS4	Balti PP total ash	70	200	150-300	300-3000	EL1
BOS5	DeSOx	70	100-200	150-300	300-3000	EL1
BOS6	Enefit280 total ash	20	100	150	3000	EL1
BOS7	Auvere PP ESPA1	20-70	200-400	300-600	300-3000	EL1
BOS8	Auvere PP total ash	20	100	150	300-3000	EL1
CDW1	CDW	-	-	-	-	-
CDW2	Concrete-CDW	70	100-200	150-200	300-3000	EL1
CDW3	Sand-CDW	-	-	-	-	-
CDW4	Washed recycled sand 0/8	-	-	-	-	-
BPD	bypass dust	70	400	300	300	EL1
NSF	Powdered blast furnace slag	70	400	300	300	EL1

Before CO₂ treatment in CM, the sample was hydrated by mixing it with water (L/S = 0.2) in the EL1 mixer for 180 s (1 kg sample at a time) at 3000 rpm. As a result, the temperature of the wet sample increased up to 60 °C. The CO₂ content in gas phase was detected by Doutec infrared analyzer and the carbonated samples were dried in thermostat for 3 h at 105 °C and analyzed for total carbon and free lime content as the main indicators for the carbonation process.

2.4. Results ad discussion

Low-grade fossil fuels such as lignite coal and oil shale generate Ca-rich ash (burnt oil shale) that contains 5 – 25% free lime. Therefore, it could be suitable material for CO₂ mineralization [14, 15, 16] by dry and wet carbonation routes [2, 12, 13].

2.4.1. Dry carbonation route

Dry carbonation tests under isothermal heating conditions by the use of TG and rotating tube furnace with pretreated BOS3, BOS7 and BPD samples (Fig. 2, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) as well as kinetic calculations have been discussed in detail by Yörük et al [17]. The TGA results indicated that hydrated samples gained the ability of higher CO₂ binding capacity for all the samples at 400 and 500 °C. About 80 – 90 % of the final uptake capacity was reached in the first 2-3 minutes at 500 °C. Although the BET surface area of both BOS and BPD samples was increased after grinding, the grounded samples that were tested at 400 – 500 °C showed an unexpected slight decrease in the reaction rates and their binding ability. It can be suggested that mechanical treatment does not enhance binding ability due to changed physical characteristics of surface effecting the absorption of CO₂. Based on the experiments and kinetic calculations, the most probable model for the carbonation process of non-hydrated BOS3 and BOS7 agrees with the three-dimensional diffusion model (D3) and the most probable model for the carbonation process of the hydrated samples and non-hydrated BPD agrees with the random nucleation and nuclei growth model (A2). The notable positive effect of hydration treatment is that the same CO₂ uptake levels can be achieved at lower operating temperatures to minimize the heat requirements for preheating the solids, thereby making the carbonation processes of similar types of industrial wastes (which are widely available) more energy efficient and thus lowering the operational and energy costs.

According to rotating tube furnace results selected types of BOS and BPD can be used as effective sorbents in the proposed CO₂ mineralization process, binding up to 0.15 kg CO₂ per kg of waste for BOS7 and 0.24 kg CO₂ per kg of waste for BPD.

2.4.2. Wet carbonation route

According to XRF analysis, the samples contained mainly Ca- and Si-compounds (Fig. 2). The phase composition indicated that the burnt oil shale samples (except BOS6) contained a considerable amount of lime, portlandite and secondary Ca-silicates, which attribute as potential CO₂ binders (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Chemical composition of tested samples.

Although the chemical composition of CDWs showed significant total calcium content (10 – 18%), the quantitative XRD indicated that the samples contained no lime or portlandite as the most active CO₂ binding phases. The sample of BPD contained significant amount of fCaO (37.49%) as lime and portlandite. Additionally, it contained 17.2% C2S, 4.0% wollastonite and 4.0% merwinite that could also be considered as CO₂ binding phases (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Phase composition of tested samples.

Theoretical CO₂ binding potential of BPD and NSF samples was very promising, especially in case of BPD, that contained 37.49% of fCaO as well as Ca-silicates. Based on the previous knowledge and chemical composition of NSF slag sample, its CO₂ binding potential is based on Ca-silicates.

Specific surface area of BOS samples varied between 1.8 m²/g to 6.1 m²/g, being higher in Auvere PP electrostatic precipitator ashes (BOS7). The mean particle sizes (d_{mean}) of total ashes (BOS2, BOS4, BOS8) were similar to the ones of electrostatic precipitator ashes of the same boilers (BOS1, BOS3, BOS7), varying from 20.98 μm in Auvere PP electrostatic precipitator ash (BOS7) to 50.62 μm in Balti PP total ash (BOS4). The exception was the BOS6 sample, which was characterized by noticeably coarser grain size. The BPD sample was a fine-grained material characterized by mean particle size of 40.87 μm and BET SSA of 3.84 m²/g. The NSF slag sample was a noticeably coarser material characterized by mean particle size of 733.68 μm and BET SSA of 4.3 m²/g. All the CDW samples were classified as 0/8 mm sand. The BET specific surface area varied from 2.2 - 10.1 m²/g (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Mean particle size (d_{mean}) and BET SSA of tested samples.

Carbonation tests showed that the free lime content could be exhausted with 30 min in the conditions of low range water solid ratio of 0.2 w/w and gas flow of 200 L/h and 70% CO_2 in air. The CO_2 uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10 – 37%) in BOS and BPD samples, but nonexistent in CDW and NSF slag. The role of Ca-Mg-silicates in the wet CO_2 mineralization route without the use of additives and increased pressure is considerably smaller. In case of fine BOS ESPA samples 5 – 12% of CO_2 bound could be attributed to Ca-silicates. Comparing different types of BOS samples indicated that fCaO content was almost fully utilized in case of fine ESPA ashes from CFB boilers, as the free lime in coarser total ashes and less porous PF ashes was only partially utilized. Changing different parameters in EL1-type intensive mixer indicated that increasing flow rates accelerated the CO_2 mineralization process due to improved contact of phases, as changing the mixing speed from 300 rpm up to 3000 rpm and changing CO_2 concentration in gas from 20% up to 70% did not affect the process remarkably. The applicability of wet carbonization process was confirmed also in larger scale by the use of a modified concrete mixer. The wet carbonation experiments have been elaborated in detail in [18].

3. Preparations for piloting

3.1. The pilot set-up

The pilot (200 L) was designed based on a commercially available concrete mixer integrated into CLEANKER Ca-looping demo system and equipped with CO₂ inlets and outlets, as well as CO₂, temperature and moisture sensors to detect the reaction progress (Fig. 5). The entry point was equipped with a perforated sleeve, variable in height, to foster the uniform spreading of gas inside the batch.

Fig. 5. Process layout.

For preliminary testing, the CO₂ gas stream was artificially prepared by mixing CO₂ and air from bottles by the means of two flow-meters allowing to vary the gas flow up to 40 L/min and the CO₂ concentration from 0 to 100% (Fig. 6). In the next stage, the pilot will be incorporated into the Ca-looping demo system, using CO₂ directly from the calciner (Fig. 5). The gas flow was homogenised in a pre-mixing chamber and flown through the first mixing chamber hosting a probe for measuring relative humidity and temperature of the inlet gas. The gas was then sent to the CO₂ mineralization reactor or, by means of a valve-controlled by-pass, directly into the CO₂ analyser (Saxon Infralyt 80). A second mixing chamber, hosting a second RH/T probe, was placed just before the analyser so that the variations in humidity and temperature taking place during the CO₂ mineralization process can be observed and recorded (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Preliminary experimental design.

Fig. 7. Testing equipment (flowmeters, mixing chambers, RH/T probes, by-pass connections, CO₂ analyzer) shown from the side (left) and from the top (right).

3.2. Preliminary results

Preliminary testing was carried out using BOS ESPA1 sample collected from Eesti PP 8K-1 on June 3rd 2020 (fCaO=7.5% and TC=0.67%). The amount of material used in a single batch was limited (40 kg) in order to control the level of wet powder and avoid crushing it against the sleeve. The operational parameters were chosen as follows: water to solid ratio was 0.2 w/w, gas flow rate and CO₂ concentration were set at 20 L/min and 50%, respectively. In the very first minutes the gas mixture was sent through the by-pass, as soon as the target CO₂ concentration (50%) was reached it was switched to the CO₂ mineralization pilot. The sudden decrease observed in the concentration of CO₂ attests that the mineralization process was taking place (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Changes in off-gas CO₂ concentration during mineralization.

Fig. 9. Relative humidity and temperature of the gas mixture before and after passing through the CO₂ mineralization pilot.

A comparison of relative humidity and temperature of the gas mixture before and after passing through the CO₂ mineralization pilot is shown in Fig 9. The variation in temperature was negligible, while the gradual increase in humidity was caused by the moistening of the gas mixture while passing through the reaction mixture.

Fig. 10. Changes in CaCO₃, Ca(OH)₂ and H₂O contents in solid samples during wet carbonation of burnt oil shale in a 200L reactor.

Solid samples were collected after every 10 – 30 minutes and submitted to TG analysis for quantification of CaCO₃ and Ca(OH)₂. Results indicated that the system saturated after 2 hours as the Ca(OH)₂ became depleted and CaCO₃ content stabilized (Fig. 10). Mixture temperature increased up to 60 °C due to exothermic effect of carbonation reaction. Preliminary testing confirmed that CO₂ could be mineralized from gas mixture by burnt oil shale in proposed wet conditions.

4. Conclusions

One of the objectives of the Horizon 2020 project CLEANKER is the construction of a CO₂ mineralization reactor for the Ca-looping demonstration system that will capture CO₂ in the cement plant operated by Buzzi Unicem sited in Vernasca. In the case of CO₂ mineralization, captured carbon dioxide gas is stored in the form of thermodynamically stable carbonate minerals, which, by eliminating the greenhouse effect of CO₂ allows environmentally safe disposal or recycling of CO₂.

The pilot testing (in 200 L reactor) was preceded by lab-experiments (in 46 L reactor), the aim of which was to select the best potential CO₂ binders and to find the optimal carbonation conditions. Laboratory tests were performed using wet and dry carbonation routes.

The results showed that selected types of burnt oil shale and cement wastes could be used as efficient binders in both dry and wet CO₂ mineralization systems with binding capacities up to 0.18 kg of CO₂ per kg of BOS and up to 0.24 kg of CO₂ per kg of CBD. The activating effect of hydration as a pre-treatment method showed that at lower operating temperatures, the same level of CO₂ capture can be achieved, thereby rendering the carbonization processes of similar industrial wastes more energy efficient. Finally, the wet carbonation route (L/S=0.2 – 0.3) was chosen for pilot testing.

The pilot (200 L) was designed based on a commercially available concrete mixer integrated into CLEANKER Ca-looping demo system and equipped with CO₂ inlets and outlets, as well as CO₂, temperature, and moisture sensors to detect the reaction progress. Preliminary testing confirmed that CO₂ could be mineralized from gas mixture by burnt

oil shale in proposed wet conditions. The testing will continue using CO₂ directly from Ca-looping calciner to produce re-carbonated wastes for concrete casting to demonstrate the quality of the commercial product in the following stages of the project.

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References

- [1] Sanna A, Uibu M, Caramanna G, Kuusik R, Maroto-Valer MM. A review of mineral carbonation technologies to sequester CO₂. *Chem Soc Rev* 2014;43:8049–80.
- [2] Sanna A, Maroto-Valer MM, editors. CO₂ sequestration by ex-situ mineral carbonation. [Hackensack] New Jersey: World Scientific; 2017.
- [3] Kuusik R, Uibu M, Kirsimäe K. Characterization of oil shale ashes formed at industrial-scale CFBC boilers. *Oil Shale* 2005;22:407–19.
- [4] Uibu M, Uus M, Kuusik R. CO₂ mineral sequestration in oil-shale wastes from Estonian power production. *J. Environ Manag* 2009;90:1253–60.
- [5] Kuusik R, Uibu M, Kirsimäe K, Mõtsep R, Meriste T. Open-air deposition of Estonian oil shale ash: formation, state of art, problems and prospects for the abatement of environmental impact. *Oil Shale* 2012;29:376–43.
- [6] Gunning PJ, Hills, CD, Carey, PJ. Production of lightweight aggregate from industrial waste and carbon dioxide. *Waste Manag* 2009; 29:2722–28.
- [7] Gastaldi D, Canonico F, Capelli L, Buzzi L, Boccaleri E, Irico S. An investigation on the recycling of hydrated cement from concrete demolition waste. *Cem Concr Compo* 2015;61:29–35.
- [8] Oliveira Andrade JJ. de, Possan E, Squiavon JZ, Ortolan TLP. Evaluation of mechanical properties and carbonation of mortars produced with construction and demolition waste. *Constr Build Mater*. 2018;161:70–83.
- [9] Barcelo L, Kline J, Walenta G, Gartner E. Cement and carbon emissions. *Mater and Struct* 2014;47:1055–65.
- [10] International Energy Agency, <https://www.iea.org/>
- [11] EU Zero Emissions Platform, <http://www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu/>
- [12] Baciocchi, R., Costa, G., Di Bartolomeo, E., Polettini, A., & Pomi, R. Wet versus slurry carbonation of EAF steel slag. *GGST Science and Technology* 2011;4:312–9.
- [13] Baciocchi, R., Costa, G., Di Gianfilippo, M., Polettini, A., Pomi, R., & Stramazzo, A. Thin-film versus slurry-phase carbonation of steel slag: CO₂ uptake and effects on mineralogy. *J Hazard Mater* 2015;283:302–313.
- [14] Uibu M, Velts O, Kuusik R. Developments in CO₂ mineral carbonation of oil shale ash. *J Hazard Mater* 2010; 174: 209–14.
- [15] Bauer M, Gassen N, Stanjek H, Peiffer S. Carbonation of lignite fly ash at ambient T and P in a semi-dry reaction system for CO₂ sequestration. *Appl. Geochemistry* 2011;26:1502–12.
- [16] Back M, Kuehn M, Stanjek H, Peiffer . Reactivity of alkaline lignite fly ashes towards CO₂ in water. *Environ Sci Technol*. 2008;42:4520–6.
- [17] Yörükcü CR, Uibu M, Usta MC, Trikkel A. CO₂ mineralization by burnt oil shale and cement bypass dust: effect of operating temperature and pre-treatment. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim*. 2020;142:991–9.
- [18] Uibu M, Tamm K, Usta MC, Žuravljova A, Kallas J, Kuusik, R, Trikkel A. Mineral Trapping of CO₂ for Cement Industry De-Carbonization. SSRN: Energy Research Network Conferences & Meetings: 14th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies Conference Melbourne 21-26 October 2018 (GHGT-14); 2019.